

THE SYSTEM OF GOVERNMENT OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE OVER THE KHIVA KHANATE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5759805>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th November 2021
Accepted: 25th November 2021
Online: 30th November 2021

KEY WORDS

Devonbegi, Young Khiva
residents, Trial, Junaydkhan,
Islamkhoja.

ABSTRACT

This article briefly describes the administrative, political and military system of government of the Khiva Khanate in the XIX century, which was a vassal of the Russian Empire, state positions and their functions.

From the second half of the 19th century, Russian rule was established over the Khiva Khanate. It was regulated by the Treaty of Friendship between Russia and Khiva of February 12, 1873. The head of state was the khan. He was bequeathed. During the stay of Russian troops in Khiva, the khan was subject only to the judiciary. Power was transferred to a special cabinet of seven people. Four of them were appointed by the governor-general. According to the treaty, the khan of Khiva had no right to establish any foreign relations, conclude agreements and conduct military operations with neighboring countries. He could communicate with the Governor-General of Turkestan only through the Amudarya branch.

After the khan, he was considered an important career partner and mehtar in the country. While the cousin was engaged in

and managed the collection of taxes from the southern part of the country, the mehtar was in charge of the northern part of the country and was mainly engaged in financial affairs.

Devonbegi headed the state office. The assignment of duties to officials was conditional, but in fact depended on the will of the khan. For example, the prime minister is sometimes a deputy, sometimes a mehtar, and sometimes a devonbeg. [1]

Administratively, the Khiva khanate was divided into twenty principalities and two deputy principalities. The principalities were governed by governors, and the nobility by deputies. Khiva, the capital of the khanate, and the surrounding districts formed a separate district, which was governed by the khan himself. The judiciary was entirely in the hands of Muslim clerics. According to the agreement of 1873, the

judiciary in the Khiva khanate was transferred to the khan. His deputy was a senior judge (senior judge) and a judge soldier.

In some places, the judiciary was in the hands of judges. There were two judges in the cities and principalities. One discussed the case and the other, the judge, oversaw the implementation of Muslim Sharia law. discussed on a customary basis in Karakalpakstan. In some cases, officials also prosecuted immigrants. [2]

The higher court was headed by a judge, whose jurisdiction included the government to hear criminal and civil cases. He also witnessed criminal and civil cases committed by the population in the khanate's capital, Khiva. Kozikalon also discussed all criminal cases that could lead to the death penalty. Cases involving the Russian population have been heard by Russian criminal and civil courts. The trial was of an indictment nature. Any case was initiated at the request of the victim. The Asfandiyarkhan period was marked by the reforms carried out by the then Prime Minister Islam Khoja and the emergence of the Young Khiva movement. But the assassination of Islamkhoja caused the reforms to stall.

In 1917, after the February Revolution, which led to the end of the Russian Empire, Khorezm regained its independence. But this independence meant isolation for Asfandiyarkhan. A new force had emerged in front of him. Inspired by the February Revolution, the "Young Khivais" began to openly continue their calls. They demanded that the khan carry out reforms. On April 4, 1917, a demonstration of several thousand people took place in front of the khan's office. Khan Polvonniyoz received a

delegation led by Hoji Yusupov and Husaynbek Matmurodov and signed a manifesto on April 5, presented by the Young Khiva. According to the document, Khorezm was designated as a constitutional monarchy. [3]

The new public administration bodies are the Court of Justice (parliament) and the Council of Ministers (Council of Ministers). Activist Boboohun Salimov has been appointed chairman of the parliament, and Husseinbek Matmurodov has been appointed head of the government. The khan also promised to build a railway, a postal and telegraph service, and new schools. But the conservative-minded khan and his allies disbanded the cabinet as a result of a military coup. By November, the meeting had also been dissolved. Reforms were suspended. [4]

Members of the "Young Khiva" who fled the country in 1918 formed the Khorezm Communist Party outside Khorezm. Its membership was 600 members. After the October coup, the Bolsheviks seized power in Russia. In Turkestan, too, power passed to the Bolsheviks. A Soviet republic was also established in Turkestan. Fearing the loss of the government in the face of Soviet threats, Asfandiyarkhan appointed a former enemy, Muhammad Qurban Sardor Junaydkhan, the leader of the Yavmut tribe of Turkmens, as commander-in-chief. Raising his position in the palace, Junaydkhan staged a coup d'etat in October 1918. Asfandiyorkhan was killed in Nurullaboy palace. His brother Said Abdullah Ghazi ascended the throne. In practice, power was concentrated in the hands of Junaid Khan. He managed to destroy all his rivals in the palace. [5]

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